

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D7.8

Final system-wide assessment on impact on jobs

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	Modelling.....	9
2.1	CGE Model	9
2.1.1	General introduction	9
2.1.2	UKENVI introduction.....	9
2.2	Parameterisation and key assumptions.....	11
3	Data	12
3.1	Social Accounting Matrix	12
3.2	Qualification data.....	13
3.3	Emissions data	14
4	CGE simulation strategy.....	14
4.1	Central scenario	14
4.2	Sensitivity analysis on LCOE estimate.....	15
4.3	Sensitivity analysis on market share.....	15
5	Results	16
5.1	Central scenario results	16
5.2	Sensitivity analysis on LCOE results	19
5.3	Sensitivity analysis on market share results	19
6	Conclusion.....	20
7	References	22

About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

Deliverable 7.8: “Final system-wide assessment on impact on jobs” aims to provide and estimate of the relationship between the expected offshore wind Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) reduction associated with X-ROTOR and key economic metrics including gross domestic product, jobs, and emissions. This report builds on the estimation of X-ROTOR LCOE undertaken in Deliverable 6.2: “Modelled LCOE for the X-ROTOR” from WP6 by using a Computerised General Equilibrium (CGE) model to model the impact of X-ROTOR.

Our UKENVI model is an energy-economy-environment CGE model based on the AMOS framework of models used extensively by the Fraser of Allander Institute (FAI). Informed by the findings of D6.2, we consider a central scenario based on the average LCOE value derived. To address uncertainty around the true LCOE of X-ROTOR we model five additional scenarios designed to test the sensitivity of our results.

List of acronyms

O&M	Operation and Maintenance
LCOE	Levelised Costs of Energy
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OWF	Offshore Wind Farm
WT	Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal-Axis Wind Turbine
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
VAWT	Vertical-Axis Wind Turbine
mr	Minor Repair
Mr	Major Repair
MR	Major Replacement
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
SAM	Social Accounting Matrix
IO	Input-Output
CES	Constant Elasticity of Substitution

1 Introduction

The X-ROTOR concept is a novel offshore wind turbine design which combines Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT) and Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine (HAWT) technology. Owing to savings from operations and maintenance expenditure (OPEX) and capital expenditure (CAPEX), initial research suggests the X-ROTOR offshore wind turbine design could reduce the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) by up to 26% (Leithhead et al., 2019). This report titled: “Final system-wide assessment on impact on jobs” provides an assessment of the contribution that reductions in LCOE associated with X-ROTOR could make to key economic metrics including gross domestic product (GDP), jobs and emissions.

One major area of ongoing research explores the possible economic impacts that the development of renewable energy could produce. Such studies often feature the application of multi-sectoral modelling approaches to explore the ex-ante consequences of such developments. Our approach utilises one such modelling framework, specifically, Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) modelling, to capture the aggregate and sectoral energy-economy-environment impacts that could arise on the UK economy from the cost reductions associated with X-ROTOR.

There are several advantages to using a CGE modelling framework for this task. Firstly, CGE models are well grounded in economic theory, providing a consistent framework for considering the whole economy impacts of policy and non-policy changes. Secondly, where the introduction of new renewable technologies produces demand as well as supply-side impacts, CGE models are well suited to analyse these, having a fully-specified demand and supply side of the economy. By contrast other types of multisectoral models, such as Input-Output provide a comparable modelling framework in which either demand or supply can be stimulated, with the other normally assumed to be entirely passive. Thirdly, a multisectoral modelling framework allows us to show how impacts in one sector/industry of the economy might then propagate across the wider economy under the specific assumptions of firm and agent behaviour incorporated, which we set out explicitly in the rest of the report.

Our use of a CGE model required the creation of a Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) as the benchmark dataset showing the interconnectedness between production and consumption. We augment the official Input Output accounts for the UK for 2018 with a novel disaggregation of the electricity sector by generation technology (see Section 3.1), while the CGE model requires an additional set of parameters to be specified (see Section 2.2).

Our methodology closely follows that of Lecca et al. (2017) in that we simulate reductions in LCOE for offshore wind in the UK as total factor productivity (TFP) improvements in the offshore wind electricity generation sector. In line with the average estimate in the LCOE X-ROTOR analysis from Deliverable 6.2, our central scenario features a 29% positive shock applied to TFP in the offshore wind electricity generation sector by 2030. In addition, we test the robustness of our results to the specific cost reduction simulated, the precise specification of the model and choice of parameters, we include two kinds of sensitivity analyses; 1) alternative reductions in LCOE; and 2) varying levels of X-ROTOR deployment by 2030.

This report is organised as follows: Section 2 discusses the key modelling assumptions – including production structure and parametrisation. Section 3 summarises the construction of the electricity disaggregated Input Output accounts and Social Accounting Matrix for the UK. Section 4 details our simulation strategy. Section 5 presents results for our central simulation and sensitivity analyses. Section 6 concludes the work by summarising the key findings and highlighting the direction for future research.

2 Modelling

2.1 CGE Model

2.1.1 General introduction

The UKENVI CGE model used in this research is an extension of the AMOS family of CGE models developed by the Fraser of Allander Institute (FAI). As noted above, a key benefit of CGE models are their economic micro-foundations for production and consumption activities in an economy. CGE models are particularly well-suited to studying the system-wide impacts of policy changes or technological improvements which impact on the supply-side of the economy and where a sectoral analysis is important. This might be either for targeting a specific disturbance in a particular economic sector or industry, or for tracking the economy-wide consequences which will impact differently across sectors of the economy in response to the change that is introduced. AMOS based CGE models have been used extensively by the FAI in both academic and policy literature to assess the macroeconomic impacts of various energy and environmental focussed shocks (Allan et al., 2008; Allan et al., 2014; Gilmartin and Allan, 2014; and Connolly, 2020). UKENVI – the CGE model employed in this analysis - is a large scale, multi-sectoral energy-economy-environment model which case been calibrated to the UK economy.

2.1.2 UKENVI introduction

The UKENVI model is a flexible framework which can be adapted to account for alternate model closures, functional forms, and parameter values. The model has 17 industry sectors – 9 of which are electricity generation sectors. See Table 1.

Table 1: Description of sectors in the UKENVI model.

17 Sectors	Sector title	113 Sectors
1	Agriculture	A01 - A03
2	Mining and Quarrying	B05 - B09
3	Manufacturing	C101 - C33Other
4	Electric power distribution, transmission, and trade	D351
5	Coal generation	D351
6	Natural gas generation	D351
7	Nuclear generation	D351
8	Hydro generation	D351
9	Onshore wind generation	D351
10	Offshore wind generation	D351
11	Biomass generation	D351
12	Solar generation	D351
13	Marine generation	D351
14	Manufacture of gas; distribution of gaseous fuels	D352
15	Water, Waste, and construction	E36 - F43
16	Wholesale and trade	G45 - G47
17	Transport and services	H49 - T97

Source: Authors' calculations

Final demand consists of four components: households, investment, government expenditure, and exports. A key assumption of the model is that producers minimise cost using a nested multilevel production function, where firms are able to substitute inputs in response to changes in prices. The model solution identifies the set of prices at which excess demand is zero in each market and market clearing prices equal

marginal costs in each sector. However, imperfect competition in the labour market is accommodated and unemployment is involuntary. A notable feature of UKENVI is that we have different production structure for the Electricity distribution, transmission and distribution sector (Diagram 2) and all other sectors (Diagram 1). The treatment of electricity in UKENVI is a point of difference to many CGE analyses, which typically have a single sector without electricity technological detail.

The general form of the production structure sees sectors producing output through a combination of intermediate inputs and value added (labour and capital). These components are combined under a Constant Elasticity of Substitution function – allowing for substitution to result from a change in input price. Intermediate inputs are either produced domestically or are imported from the rest of the world (ROW) and are combined based on the Armington function (Armington, 1969). Changes in the relative price of these components leads to substitution through the assumption of Constant Elasticity of Substitution. Sectors are able to substitute Electricity for Non-electricity intermediate goods, while only the Electricity distribution, transmissions and distribution sector is able to make purchases of different electricity generation technologies output. We assume that Non-electricity intermediate goods are consumed in line with the Leontief function based on the UK Input-Output Table.

Diagram 1: Production function for all sectors in UKENVI (apart from Electricity distribution, transmission and trade)

Source: FAI

Diagram 2: Production function for Electricity distribution, transmission and trade sector

Source: FAI

As can be seen in Diagram 2 the Electricity node is a composite of Electricity generation and Electricity supply i.e., distribution, transmission and trade. This unique structure implies that all output from the Electricity generation sectors is sold to a single Electricity supply sector, which then provides Non-electricity sectors with electricity. This sector acts as a mediator between the Electricity generation sectors e.g., Offshore, Solar, and Coal and the rest of the economy. Generation is a combination of Offshore renewables and Non-offshore generation. Offshore renewables technologies include Wind (Onshore and Offshore) and Marine. Non-offshore generation technologies include Coal, Gas, Nuclear, Hydro, Biomass, and solar.

We can run simulations in both dynamic and static configurations. In the report we present the long-run results of simulations in which TFP in the Offshore generation sector is stimulated (increased). The assessment here is not focussed on the dynamics of the shock and therefore, we report results for the long-run i.e., once capital stocks have fully adjusted to the shock. The model features forward looking agents and a single labour market with no migration where workers have perfect mobility between sectors. Wages are determined through a bargaining function where workers with higher bargaining power can leverage higher wages. Meaning that, ultimately, the real wage is inversely related to the unemployment rate.

Section 2.2 will provide further details on the parameters, market closure, and dynamic specification of the UKENVI model.

2.2 Parameterisation and key assumptions

As noted in Lecca et al. (2017), the specification of the UKENVI model and the specific elasticity values chosen will impact on the results from the UKENVI model. Elasticity of substitution is a measure of how easy it is to substitute one input for another and can take any value between 1 and ∞ . Elasticities that are equal to 1 imply unitary elasticity, while lower values indicate moving towards difficult to exchange inputs until 0 where inputs are considered perfect compliments. Higher values indicate a higher degree of substitutability between inputs.

In the interests of transparency, Table 2 presents the values for the Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) productions functions used in the central scenario. The elasticities used in the model are motivated by a review of the literature and in particular those used by Lecca et al. (2017). When we perform sensitivity analysis later, we restrict this to alternative values for reductions in LCOE for Offshore wind.

Table 2: Elasticities of substitution used in UKENVI

Node	Elasticity
Armington Elasticity: between imports and domestic output in domestic demand	2
CET Elasticity: between exports and domestic supplies in domestic market output	2
Between Factors	
Wage differential	1
Between Intermediate and Value Added	0.3
Between Electricity and Non-Electricity	0.3
Generation and Supply	0.3
Between Intermittent and Non-Intermittent	5
Between Non-offshore generation	5
Between Wind and Marine	5
Between Onshore wind and Offshore wind	5

Source: Authors' calculation based on simulation results

Consistent with Lecca et al. (2017) and Connolly (2019), many CES functions in the UKENVI model are set to a default elasticity of substitution equal to 0.3. For the purpose of this report, the most important elasticities relate to the functions concerning electricity. We adopt an elasticity of substitution between generation technologies equal to 5 – once again consistent with those used in Lecca et al. (2017) and Connolly (2019).

3 Data

3.1 Social Accounting Matrix

The UKENVI model used in this report is calibrated on purpose-built SAM for the UK economy in 2018. This SAM combines data from national economic accounts such as the income-expenditure accounts and a novel electricity generation disaggregated Input-Output (IO) table.

The standard IO table for the UK contains a single entry for the generation, distribution, transmission, and trade of electricity. There are two drawbacks to this level of aggregation: (1) no distinction is made between the income and expenditures of these activities – while generation and distribution likely require different inputs, this granularity is lost; (2) there is no distinction between the different technologies generating electricity i.e., electricity produced with coal, wind, and solar is undifferentiated. Our modelling approach requires an electricity generation disaggregated IO table which details both incomes and expenditures of the electricity generating technologies.

Our disaggregation process, at its simplest level, resembles the “top down” approach applied by Gay and Proops (1993) and follows many of their early works core assumptions. First, electricity producing sectors sell only to the electricity distribution sector. Second, Fuel inputs than can easily be identified are allocated to the relevant generation technology i.e., the purchase of coal is attributed to the coal electricity generation sector. Thirdly, remaining inputs are split based on the generation technology share of total electricity generated in the base year. If offshore wind was responsible for 20% of electricity generated, then they are allocated 20% of the purchase of certain inputs. More in line with the “hybrid” approach of

Connolly (2019), this disaggregation augments the traditional approach by using “bottom up” data from a wide range of sources. Employment estimates for the electricity generation, distribution, trade and transmission sector were sourced from the Business Register and Employment Survey (ONS, 2022) while generation technology specific employment estimates from the UK Energy Research Centre “Green Job Creation, quality and skills report (Hanna, Heptonstall, and Gross, 2022) were used in our estimations. A full description of the data sources used in our disaggregation can be found in Appendix A.

The result of our efforts was a 113-sector electricity generation disaggregated IO table for the UK for 2018 – containing nine electricity sectors, with one sector capturing the distribution, transmission, and trade of electricity (non-generation) and eight sectors for electricity generation: Coal, Natural Gas, Nuclear, Hydro, Onshore, Offshore, Solar, and Other.

3.2 Qualification data

To speak to metrics of ‘green jobs’ we focus on the impact of X-ROTOR on jobs which require highly qualified employees. In recent years there has been much debate on the difficulties of defining and measuring ‘green jobs’ which has led to a greater of concepts such as the ‘just transition’ which requires a focus on increasing the quantity of ‘good quality’ and ‘well-paid’ jobs.

We use data from the Q1 2018 UK Labour Force Survey (ONS, 2018) to estimate the impact of X-ROTOR on jobs with a focus on employee qualification level. We define “high qualification” jobs as those where employees hold qualifications equal to or greater than level 3 in the UK National Framework of Qualifications (NQF). Level 3 in the UK’s NQF is on par with Level 4 in the European Qualifications Framework (EQF).

Table 3: High and low qualification shares by sector (%)

Sector	Low Qualification	High Qualification
Agriculture	58%	42%
Mining and Quarrying	31%	69%
Manufacturing	43%	57%
Electric power transmission and distribution	26%	74%
Nuclear generation	26%	74%
Coal generation	26%	74%
Hydro generation	26%	74%
Natural gas generation	26%	74%
Other generation (Biomass)	26%	74%
Onshore generation	26%	74%
Offshore generation	26%	74%
Solar generation	26%	74%
Other generation (Marine)	26%	74%
Manufacture of gas	28%	72%
Water, Waste, and construction	43%	57%
Wholesale and trade	54%	46%
Transport and Services	31%	69%

Source: Labour Force Survey and authors’ calculations

As can be seen from Table 3, the LFS does not provide electricity generation technology disaggregated qualification level data. As a result, the qualification share for the Electricity generation, distribution, transmission, and trade sector was applied to all generation technologies. In our model we calculate the

impact on full-time equivalent jobs and apply the above shares to determine the change in high and low qualification jobs.

3.3 Emissions data

We are also interested in demonstrating the consequences of cost reductions in offshore wind for UK emissions. Specifically, we focus on emissions from fuel use in industrial production (i.e., emissions by sectors/industries from their consumption of fuels), and so do not consider the impact on changes in emissions from household's direct energy consumption which includes private transport and emissions from direct fuel use in households, e.g., gas or coal. Sectoral fuel use data consists of purchases of coal, oil, gas, diesel and petrol, fuel oil, gas oil, aviation fuel, and "Other" (ONS, 2022). Emissions from each fuel are calculated using emission conversion factors (DBEIS and DEFRA, 2021).

In our model, we link energy consumption by fuel use to sectors purchases of commodities, we can thus calculate changes in sectoral (and therefor aggregate) emissions from the changes in the purchases of energy inputs by sectors. Emissions changes in aggregate are the sum of sectoral emissions changes, where the emissions intensity of energy consumption by fuel is fixed at the initial values. Of this total, 35% comes from the consumption of natural gas, with significant contributions from Aviation Fuel (16%), Diesel (15%) and Coal (10%).

Sectors purchases of fuels are linked to changes in sectors consumptions of goods containing fuels, so that changes in purchases of Mining and Quarrying related to changes in sectoral purchases of coal, Manufacturing (containing oil refining production) is related to changes in the consumption of gas and oils, and Wholesale and Retail (including purchases from petrol stations) is used as the change in consumption of petrol and diesel by sector. In all, industrial emissions from fuel use by UK industries in our base year dataset for 2018 constitute total emissions of 292.15 MtCO₂e.

4 CGE simulation strategy

4.1 Central scenario

With the UKENVI model appropriately calibrated to the UK economy, we were then ready to determine the series of shocks to apply to the Offshore wind generation sector. Final LCOE estimates from D6.2 presented below in Table 4, were our main inputs in determining our simulations.

Table 4: X-ROTOR LCOE estimates for projects commissioned in 2030¹

	<i>X-ROTOR LCOE 2030 (MW/h)</i>
Average	€46.74
Low	€43.05
High	€50.44

Source: Deliverable 6.2

Our approach was to calculate the percentage reduction in LCOE associated with X-ROTOR in 2030 relative to current estimates produced by BEIS for traditional wind turbines in 2025.

BEIS (2020) provide LCOE estimates for offshore wind projects commissioned in the near future in their 2020 Electricity Generation Costs report. This report provides a figure of approximately €66.12 MW/h for offshore wind projects commissioned in 2025 which we take as our base year.

Equation 1 presents the calculation for the percentage change in LCOE associated with X-ROTOR. The average X-ROTOR final LCOE estimate from Table 4 is considered relative to the BEIS 2025 estimate - suggesting that X-ROTOR turbines commissioned in 2030 will have an improved LCOE of 29% relative to close-to-current estimates of traditional turbines in 2025. See Equation 1.

Equation 1:

$$LCOE\ reduction = 1 - \left(\frac{Average\ LCOE_{2030}^{XRC}}{LCOE_{2025}^{BEIS}} \right) = 1 - \left(\frac{€46.74\ MW/h}{€66.12\ MW/h} \right) = 29\%$$

We closely follow the one-for-one LCOE to TFP translation used by Lecca et al. (2017) and interpret the 29% LCOE reduction associated with X-ROTOR as a 29% improvement in TFP to be applied to the Offshore wind electricity generation sector.

4.2 Sensitivity analysis on LCOE estimate

Estimating LCOE values is a complex process, especially for new technologies. There are many variables and considerable variation between how different government agencies around the world calculate LCOE. Deliverable 6.2 acknowledges the many uncertainties that impact the estimation of LCOE and provide a range of final estimates that include Low and High LCOE estimates. See Table 4.

The first set of sensitivity analyses contained in this report are focused on LCOE variation. We determine these two shocks following the calculation laid-out in Equation 1, changing only the Average LCOE estimate for the Low (€43.05) and High (€50.44) estimates.

Equation 2:

$$SA1 = 1 - \left(\frac{LOW\ LCOE_{2030}^{XRC}}{LCOE_{2025}^{BEIS}} \right) = 1 - \left(\frac{€43.05\ MW/h}{€66.12\ MW/h} \right) = 35\%$$

Equation 3:

$$SA2 = 1 - \left(\frac{HIGH\ LCOE_{2030}^{XRC}}{LCOE_{2025}^{BEIS}} \right) = 1 - \left(\frac{€50.44\ MW/h}{€66.12\ MW/h} \right) = 24\%$$

4.3 Sensitivity analysis on market share

This sensitivity analysis addresses the key assumption in the previous scenarios that, in 2030, offshore wind turbines will be entirely X-ROTOR. To address this assumption, we consider three scenarios where X-ROTOR accounts for 25%, 50% and 75% of offshore wind turbines operating with the remainder being traditional HAWTs. The LCOE value for X-ROTOR is the central estimate used in the central scenario, while the HAWT 2030 estimate comes from the 2020 Cost of Electricity Generation report for traditional offshore wind (BEIS, 2020).

Equation 4.1 shows the general formula used to calculate the weighted average LCOE reduction of X-ROTOR and HAWTs. Equation 4.2 corresponds to sensitivity analyses three (SA3), where 25% of turbines are X-ROTOR and 75% are HAWTs.

$$\text{Equation 4.1 } \textit{General specification} = 1 - \left(\left(\frac{LCOE_{2030}^{XRC}}{LCOE_{2025}^{BEIS}} * X \right) + \left(\frac{LCOE_{2030}^{BEIS}}{LCOE_{2025}^{BEIS}} * (1 - X) \right) \right)$$

$$\text{Equation 4.2 } SA3 = 1 - \left(\left(\frac{€46.74}{€66.12} * 0.25 \right) + \left(\frac{€54.52}{€66.12} * 0.75 \right) \right) = 20\%$$

Table 5 summarises or simulation strategy presenting the level of TFP shock applied to the Offshore wind sector in each simulation. As can be seen from above, Equation 4.2 corresponds to the TFP shock applied in SA3.

Table 5: Central and sensitivity analysis TFP shocks

	TFP shock (%)
Central scenario: X-ROTOR average LCOE with 100% market share	29%
SA1: X-ROTOR LOW LCOE with 100% market share	35%
SA2: X-ROTOR HIGH LCOE with 100% market share	24%
SA3: X-ROTOR central LCOE with 25% market share	20%
SA4: X-ROTOR central LCOE with 50% market share	23%
SA5: X-ROTOR central LCOE with 75% market share	26%

Source: Authors' calculation based on simulation results

5 Results

5.1 Central scenario results

Table 6 presents long-run results for key macroeconomic indicators for our central scenario. In the central scenario a 29% improvement in total factor productivity – i.e., an expansion in the amount which can be produced for a given set of inputs – is introduced to the Offshore wind electricity generation sector. This will lower the cost of producing electricity from this technology relative to others, encouraging expansion of the use of offshore wind and lowering the price of electricity other things being equal. Note we do not introduce any other change or disturbance to the simulation, either a policy action or otherwise, so this improvement is modelled as having zero cost. The long-run here corresponds to the point at which capital stocks fully adjust to the productivity shock i.e., where rental rates and the user cost of capital are equalised. The results in Table 6 are presented as the percentage change from the initial baseline – which repeats in the absence of any disturbance - unless otherwise stated.

Table 6: System-wide impact of X-ROTOR on aggregate economic metrics, % change from baseline unless otherwise stated.

	Long-run results
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	0.48
GDP (£M)	9,620
Consumer Price Index (CPI)	0.20
Unemployment Rate	-1.86
Total Employment	0.12
FTE employment	29,540
High Qualification FTE	20,030

Low Qualification FTE	9,510
Nominal Gross Wage	0.41
Real Gross Wage	0.21
Real Wage after Tax	0.21
Replacement cost of capital	0.19
Households Consumption	0.31
Net investment	0.63
Capital Stock	0.63
Export	-0.20
Emissions from industrial fuel use (MtCO ₂ e)	-10.03
Emissions from industrial fuel use (%)	-3.43

Source: Authors' calculation based on simulation results

In summary, a 29% increase in total factor productivity in the Offshore wind generation sector yields a substantial, positive impact on economic activity in the long-run. As can be seen in Table 6, UK GDP increases by 0.48% or around £9.6bn. This impact is noteworthy, given the sector's contribution to the UK's GDP in the base year was relatively small, at just 0.04% of overall value of economic activity.

This increase is roughly three times as large as the 0.15% increase in GDP found by Lecca et al. (2017) for a similar reduction in cost of offshore wind. The difference can largely be accounted for by the substantial expansion of the offshore wind electricity sector in the past decade. In 2010, the base year used by Lecca et al. (2017), offshore wind generated about 3 terawatt-hours (TW/h) of electricity, constituting just 1% of the UK's total energy mix. However, by our base year 2018, offshore wind had grown considerably to 27 TW/h, making up 8% of the total energy mix (BEIS, 2019).

In the first-order effect electricity becomes cheaper to produce in the Offshore wind sector relative to baseline. Insofar as the parameters in the model allow for substitution to take place, this creates an increase in demand for electricity generated by the Offshore wind sector.

In the short-run the increased demand for offshore wind leads to a higher rate of return to capital in the Offshore wind sector; this incentivises investment in expanding the capital stock in this sector. In the long-run the UKENVI model fully adjusts to the shock and equalises the rate of return to capital in the economy at a new higher level of 0.19% relative to baseline. The capital stock increases by 0.63% on average across the economy and by just under 430% in the Offshore wind generation sector. Our results also show a 0.2% decrease in net exports (exports minus imports) due to a decrease in export competitiveness from the small increase in CPI.

Moving alongside the capital adjustment is the impact on total employment from the new demand. The UKENVI model permits intersectoral labour mobility but no migration into the UK, i.e., the population is assumed to be fixed. With no external source of labour supply, the increased demand for labour indicated by the 0.12% increase in total employment leads to a 1.86 percentage point reduction in the unemployment rate (and an increase in the participation rate).

The 0.12% increase in total employment translates to an increase of approximately 29,540 full-time equivalent (FTE) jobs across the UK. Using data from the UK Labour Force Survey we estimate that 20,030 of these jobs could be "high qualification" jobs where employees hold qualifications equal to or above level 3 in the UK National Framework of Qualifications (NQF) (i.e., level 4 under the EQF).

Chart 1 shows the change in FTE employment across the sectors of the UKENVI model by qualification level. It is important to note that when the supply side of the economy is considered, there are always winners and losers in the wake of an economic shock, particularly given our assumption that the labour supply is fixed in aggregate. Here we see that, while on balance the shock drives an aggregate increase in employment – this is not the case for all sectors. We see both the Mining and quarrying, and the Services

and Transport sectors experience a reduction in FTE employment with a greater loss of high qualification works than low qualification workers. This loss is more than made up for by the increase in Manufacturing, Construction, and Offshore wind sectors. These results highlight the potential for X-ROTOR to drive growth in high-quality jobs.

Chart 1: FTE employment change across sectors by qualification

Source: Authors' calculations based on CGE results

Due to the inverse relationship between the unemployment rate and wages, this change feeds through to a 0.41% increase in the nominal wage and a 0.21% increase in the real wage. The increase in total employment in the economy leads to a higher absolute level of disposable income and thus drives the 0.31% increase in household consumption – relative to baseline.

Following the supply side shock and subsequent change in demand for industrial fuels, we can see that in the long-run industrial fuel decreased by 3.43% from baseline – equivalent to an absolute reduction of approximately 10.03 metric tonnes of CO₂. This is a significant result in the context of an overall increase in economic activity. However, it is worth noting that only emission changes from industrial fuel use is considered here and not changing fuel use from other sources such as the increase in household consumption.

Sorrell (2008) defines the rebound effect as occurring when an improvement in efficiency – here in the Offshore wind generation sector - leads to an increase in demand that partially or full offsets the decrease in demand driven by efficiency gains. Our results suggest that a “backfire” effect – a version of rebound where the second order increase in demand surpasses the decrease from improved efficiency – is taking place. We see an increase in total electricity consumption of 5.01% overall. This effect ultimately drives a small increase in the consumer price index of 0.2% and is likely attributable to the high elasticity of substitution set between the electricity generation technologies.

5.2 Sensitivity analysis on LCOE results

To support the results from our central scenario, this section presents results from a sensitivity analysis around the X-ROTOR LCOE estimate and thus the size of the TFP shock applied. See Equation 2 and 3 from Section 4.2.

Table 7 presents results from Low and High LCOE scenarios based on the range of estimates presented in D6.2. In the LOW scenario, where the estimated LCOE value is lowest and thus the TFP shock is highest, GDP increases by 0.72% - approximately £14.4bn. In the High scenario GDP increases by 0.33% or a little over £6.6bn. While not all impacts are linear, the direction of effect on all variables are consistent as the magnitude of the shock changes. Total employment increases by 0.18% in the Low scenario, while in the High scenario the increase is 0.08%.

Table 7: Systemwide impact of Low and High LCOE scenarios, % change from baseline unless otherwise stated

	Low LCOE	High LCOE
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	0.72	0.33
GDP (£M)	14,430	6,610
Consumer Price Index (CPI)	0.30	0.13
Unemployment Rate (%)	-2.75	-1.27
Total Employment	0.18	0.08
Nominal Gross Wage	0.62	0.28
Real Gross Wage	0.32	0.14
Real Wage after Tax	0.32	0.14
Replacement cost of capital	0.29	0.13
Households Consumption	0.46	0.22
Net investment	0.92	0.44
Capital Stock	0.92	0.44
Export	-0.30	-0.14

Source: Authors' calculation based on simulation results

5.3 Sensitivity analysis on market share results

In this section, we present a further sensitivity analysis aimed at addressing a key assumption around X-ROTOR's market share in our central scenario. The scenarios modelled previously in Section 4.1 and Section 4.2 assume that LCOE estimates for X-ROTOR represent the entire sector i.e., all offshore wind turbines are X-ROTOR. We relax this assumption and model three scenarios where the shock is a weighted average of the central X-ROTOR LCOE estimate and the estimated LCOE for traditional HAWTs (BEIS, 2020) – altering the proportion X-ROTOR turbines to 25%, 50%, and 75%. See Equation 4 and Table 5 for further details.

Table 8 presents results for key macroeconomic indicators for the market share analysis. At 25% market share, GDP increases by 0.23% - just under half of the increase seen in our baseline scenario at 100% market share. At 50% and 75% market share, GDP increases by 0.30% and 0.39% relative to the base year, respectively.

At 25% market share, total employment increases by 0.06% and the unemployment rate decreases by 0.9%. At 50% market share, total employment increases by 0.07%, while the unemployment rate decreases by 1.17%. Total employment increases by 0.10% in the 75% market share scenario leading to a decrease of in the unemployment rate of 1.49%.

Table 8: Macroeconomic impacts of 25%, 50% and 75% market share scenarios, % change from baseline unless otherwise stated

	25% Market share	50% Market share	75% Market share
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	0.23	0.30	0.39
GDP (£M)	4,610	6,010	7,820
Consumer Price Index (CPI)	0.09	0.12	0.16
Unemployment Rate (%)	-0.90	-1.17	-1.49
Total Employment	0.06	0.07	0.10
Nominal Gross Wage	0.19	0.25	0.33
Real Gross Wage	0.10	0.13	0.17
Real Wage after Tax	0.10	0.13	0.17
Replacement cost of capital	0.09	0.12	0.15
Households Consumption	0.16	0.20	0.25
Net investment	0.32	0.41	0.51
Capital Stock	0.32	0.41	0.51
Export	-0.09	-0.12	-0.16

Source: Authors' calculation based on simulation results

6 Conclusion

The primary objective of this report was to conduct a comprehensive system-wide assessment of X-ROTOR's impact on job creation within the UK economy. To achieve this objective, we employed the UKENVI CGE model, calibrated with a novel disaggregation of the 2018 UK Input-Output table focused on electricity generation. This paper builds on recent papers investigating the impact of improvements in offshore wind electricity generation productivity. Our novel disaggregation provides an up-to-date database for future research measuring the economic impact of the offshore wind sector in the UK.

In conclusion, the economy-wide analysis reveals the potential positive impact of X-ROTOR - an innovative offshore wind turbine technology - on macroeconomic metrics such as GDP, employment and emissions. Our central simulation illustrates that the expected LCOE reduction associated with X-ROTOR has the capacity to increase UK economic activity by approximately £9.6 billion or 0.48% of the nation's GDP.

Moreover, our results suggest a significant and positive impacts on jobs, with an estimated increase in total employment of approximately 0.12%, equivalent to the creation of over 29,540 full-time equivalent jobs, including approximately 20,030 high qualification positions. It is worth noting that the robustness of these estimates is underpinned by the consistency of results across varying scenarios when alternative productivity shocks are simulated.

Our results also highlight the net-positive impact on emissions from reduced industrial fuel use from X-ROTOR. Overall, UK emissions from industrial fuel use fell by 10.03 MtCO_{2e} – approximately 3.4% lower than the baseline value.

Interestingly, our findings shed light on the capacity of a relatively small sector - offshore wind - which accounted for just 0.04% of the UK's GDP in our base year, to impact the broader economy. Our results underscore the potential for economic gains to be achieved in the event that the LCOE of offshore wind technologies can be reduced.

However, there are several limitations to keep in mind when interpreting the results presented in this analysis. Firstly, as with all CGE models, our analysis required the selection of certain parameters, labour market closures, and model specifications, which may influence simulation outcomes. Notably, setting the elasticity of substitution between generation technologies set equal to 5 may result in higher levels of substitution between generation technologies than is realistic. Research determining a reasonable range of these parameters is still sparse – leading us to follow the assumptions of Lecca et al. (2017) and Connolly (2019). Furthermore, limitations related to the supply side of the economy, particularly the absence of labour migration within the UKENVI model, could potentially overestimate the impact on employment and wages.

Assessing the impact of X-ROTOR on the creation of ‘good quality’ and ‘well-paid’ jobs provides a model of how the move towards a renewable energy economy could facilitate a ‘just transition’. Our analysis included an examination of X-ROTOR's impact on employment by qualification category. This category provides details of the kind of qualification held by workers by sector, while the approach could also be used to elaborate on the occupations or skills by workers in each industry were similar data to be available. An additional aspect of the energy transition would capture regional concentration within industries and the impacts by region, which is beyond the scope of our national analysis.

We anticipate that future research will benefit from forthcoming data releases by the Office for National Statistics (ONS) regarding the sectoral definition of 'green Jobs,' allowing for a more detailed exploration of X-ROTOR's impact.

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